

Whitepaper on the measurement of hydrophobicity, hydrophilicity, and wettability

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7181091

Date: 10-10-2022

Version: 1.0

This whitepaper is based on the work within the EMPIR project MFMET - Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices. The project focuses on providing generic methodologies of accurate measurement of key quantities in microfluidic devices, utilising or developing standardised methods and reference documents. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu. The work on this paper has been supported by the Microfluidics Association (www.microfluidics-association.org) The Microfluidics Association is founded by a group of organizations working in the field of microfluidics. The Association brings interested parties together to initiate and follow up actions to promote the microfluidic industry and published several guidelines for microfluidics design and fabrication.

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Introduction

This whitepaper is written to provide information and procedures to test the hydrophobicity, hydrophilicity, and wettability, focused on microfluidic device applications. The methods used ensure traceability to national standards and conformity to existing normative standards.

Microfluidics, concerned with fluid-handling in the nano-to-millilitre scale, has major applications in biomedical and chemical analysis. At these small scales surface tension forces play a major role in fluid dynamics and therefore must be understood by microfluidics engineers and scientists. Surface tension forces are influenced by surface properties like texture, surface energy etc. and result in specific interaction of liquid and surface. Understanding that interaction is key to understand microfluidic flow properties as resistivity and fouling, i.e., key performance parameters of microfluidic devices. The interaction is generally expressed as hydrophobicity, hydrophilicity, and wettability. Efficient and correct measurement of these quantities is therefore needed.

Definitions of surface properties¹

The surface property **wettability** is the degree by which a liquid is spread over a surface, i.e., the degree of **wetting** (adhesive contact between solid and liquid). The **contact angle** (wetting angle) is a quantitative measure of the wettability of a solid by a liquid, represented by the angle formed between the solid/liquid interface and the liquid/vapor interface². The measured contact angle is independent of geometry and hence is a material property, but depends on several factors, such as surface energy, surface chemistry, surface roughness/texture, the manner of surface preparation, surface cleanliness, and on the properties of liquid and vapor phases.

Interfacial free energy, or interfacial tension, γ , arises from the energy or tension resulting from intermolecular forces on interfaces. This term, interfacial free energy, expressed in mJ/m^2 , is contributed from the existence of an interface between two co-existing phases (liquid-liquid or liquid-solid), which is also called interfacial tension expressed in mN/m . The respective indices “l” for liquid and “s” for solid indicate the phases involved.

Surface free energy, γ_{sv} , or free energy of the surface, arises from the interfacial free energy of a solid surface in contact with the vapour phase (“v” represents vapour phase). Usually, the surface free energy is not measured directly, instead, it is presented by the help of surface tension of the liquid and the contact angle mentioned below.

Surface tension, γ_{lv} , is an interfacial tension of a **liquid surface** in equilibrium with its vapour phase (lv), resulting from the asymmetrical intermolecular forces on interfaces due to the low molecule density on the vapour side. The surface tension is indicated as force per unit length (mN/m). it is introduced to take into account the excess of the surface energy due to the asymmetrical molecular interactions.

Contact angle and wettability

Imagine a droplet of liquid being observed on a homogeneous and relatively flat surface. The contact angle is defined as the angle between the tangent to the solid-liquid interface (sl) and the tangent to the liquid-vapor/gas (lv) interface. In Figure 1 the **contact angle**, is annotated as the angle to the base line within the drop, formed by means of a tangent on the drop contour at the contact line where the solid, the liquid and the vapour phases meet, which is indicated by the contact points from the side view in figure 1

Figure 1 – a) Definition of contact angle for an ideal surface. Surface free energy (γ_{sv}), interfacial free energy (γ_{sl}) and surface tension (γ_{lv}) are also represented, b) contact angle at a solid-liquid-gas contact line

¹ ISO 19403-1: 2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 1: Terminology and general principles

² de Gennes, P.-G. (1985). Wetting—statics and dynamics, *Reviews of Modern Physics* 57:827-863, doi: 10.1103/RevModPhys.57.827

The Young's equation is used to describe the equilibrium between the forces of cohesion and adhesion which shape the droplet and measure what is referred to as surface free energy γ_{sv} or interfacial energy γ .

$$\gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl} - \gamma_{lv} \cos\theta_e = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where γ_{sv} , γ_{sl} and γ_{lv} are respectively the surface free energy of the solid-vapor, solid-liquid, and liquid-vapor interfaces. θ_e is the equilibrium contact angle defined in the figure above.

Using the contact angle, θ_e , one can describe the wettability of a solid surface using the terms hydrophilicity and hydrophobicity (see also figure 2). On a hydrophobic surface, a small amount of liquid forms a droplet with high contact angles ($\theta_e > 90^\circ$) and the surface is said to be hydrophobic³. This condition is exemplified by poor wetting, poor adhesiveness and the solid surface free energy is low. If the liquid is attracted by the solid, the contact angles are low ($\theta_e < 90^\circ$). This hydrophilic condition reflects better wetting, better adhesiveness, and higher surface energy. Contact angles $\theta_e < 10^\circ$ describe superhydrophilic surfaces and $\theta_e > 150^\circ$ gives superhydrophobic surfaces.

Figure 2 – Degree of wettability/contact angle versus surface energy.

Although strictly speaking not accurate, generally people call a material with a contact angle between 0° and 90° wettable and above 90° it is called not wettable. In the case of complete wetting (spreading), the contact angle $\theta_e = 0^\circ$. In the case of superhydrophobic materials with the so-called *lotus effect*, the contact angle approaches the theoretical limit of 180° ; this can only be achieved through structuring/functionalizing the surface.

³ In this whitepaper we discuss only the wettability of water-based fluids.

Measuring the contact angle of a droplet on a flat surface.

Introduction

In practice microfluidic engineers and scientists test the wettability of a certain material using water, but other fluids can be used.

There are several ways of measuring the contact angle, but the most common method for measurement of the contact angle involves looking at the profile of the droplet formed on the surface and measuring two-dimensionally the angle formed among the solid the vapour and the liquid (droplet profile) at the three-phase contact line. Two methods are possible:

1) static contact angle measurement

On a droplet shortly after its creation when the droplet is in static state, the static contact angle is captured. Static contact angle provides valuable information about the properties of the surface and can be used when the surface properties are homogenous. For a real surface, the hysteresis exists due to the irregularities of the surface, so the static contact angle is a value between the advancing and receding contact angles of the droplet just before it about to advances/recedes, which are introduced below.

2) dynamic contact angle measurement

When the surface is inhomogeneous static contact angle measurement can lead to incorrect results. In those cases, dynamic contact angle measurement is more appropriate. Such measurement, as represented in figure 3, requires adding volume to the droplet dynamically to the maximum volume permitted without increasing the three-phase line. The resulting maximum possible contact angle is the advancing angle. Volume is then removed from the droplet. When reaching the maximum volume that can be removed without reducing the three-phase line, the resulting contact angle is measured. This angle is the receding angle. Receding and advancing contact angles show the range of the contact angles that a droplet can maintain on the surface, which are caused by the contact angle hysteresis of a real surface. Contact angle hysteresis is quantitatively expressed by the difference between advancing and receding contact angle.

Figure 3. Dynamic sessile droplet method. a) advancing contact angle and b) receding contact angle

General test protocol

The general test protocol to measure contact angles on flat surfaces is described in ISO 19403-2⁴, section 7 “Procedure”:

- The contact angle measuring system should be free of vibrations, intense air flow, intense exposure to light from the outside. The system should be aligned horizontally.
- Testing should be carried out at 23 ± 2 °C and a relative humidity at 50 ± 5 %, the test media should have the same temperature.
- The sample specimen should be placed on a sample holder, its height should be positioned in the lower half of the image and horizontally aligned.
- The chosen test liquid should be prepared and filled in a syringe without contamination or bubbles.
- The needle/cannula is moved in the upper margin of the image; focus, contrast and brightness should be adjusted. The magnification should be adjusted to have the width of the contour of the drop to take up 2/3 of the measurement image.
- Sets of contact angle reference standards for the Young-Laplace method can be used to validate this method with an accuracy of 0.1 °. The angle reference standard itself should be calibrated and the values obtained provided in a calibration certificate issued by an ISO 17025 accredited laboratory.

Static method from ISO 19403-2:2017:

- The dosing needle/cannula is positioned 3-6 mm above the surface of the test specimen. The volume of the test drop should be between 2-6 μ l.
- Apply/transfer one drop to the surface.
- Align the baseline intersecting the three-phase point (solid surface-liquid phase-gas phase). **The angle is formed between the tangent of the drop curve and the baseline.**
- The contact angle should be measured immediately after the drop gets in contact with the test specimen.
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Figure 3 –Image resulting of the measurement of static contact angle on an optical tensiometer using the sessile droplet method.

⁴ ISO 19403-2:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 2: Determination of the surface free energy of solid surfaces by measuring the contact angle

Limitation of measurement of a contact angle on a flat surface for microfluidic devices

Although the methods described above for the measurement of the static and dynamic contact angles on flat surfaces give a good picture of the wettability of a certain material, it has limited predictive value for the wettability in real life situation. In real life the material has gone through processing to transformed it into a microfluidic device. The processing conditions might influence the wettability of the processed material inside a small channel, which is the quantity of interest.

To measure contact angles in channels, one should consider the cross section of a channel to be more or less round/circular. It should also be mentioned that for semi-circular cross-sections of channels edge effects influence the contact angle and thus no clear categorization of the wetting behaviour can be made as in the case of flat surfaces. There are various approaches in research and publications to measure the contact angle in fully circular cross-sectional channels⁵, but up to this date there is no uniform, validated, and unambiguous method for measuring it. Measurement setup and devices for such purposes are also not defined in a uniform way or even to be purchased. This is seen as a serious matter for microfluidic flow control.

It is planned to test the feasibility of using the present measurement protocol for contact angles in channels under project MFMET. The present white paper will be updated based on the results obtained.

⁵ [See list art the end of this whitepaper.](#)

Calculation of the surface free energy of a solid

There is no direct measurement method for the surface free energy of a solid; γ_{sv} it must be calculated from other measurements as shown below.

An equilibrium of vectorial forces dictates the contact angle θ_e at the three-phase contact line of a deposited drop. The surface energy of the solid, γ_{sv} acts along the solid surface. The solid-liquid interfacial energy, γ_{sl} acts in the opposite direction and the surface tension γ_{lv} of the liquid acts tangential to the drop surface. This can be described by a simple scalar equation, the Young's equation (Equation 2).

$$\gamma_{lv} \cdot \cos(\theta_e) = \gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl} \quad (2)$$

To determine the **surface free energy of a solid**, γ_{sv} one measures the contact angles, θ_e of test liquids whose surface tensions, γ_{lv} including their dispersive ("d") and polar ("p") parts are known. These dispersive and polar parts are used to calculate the interfacial tension, γ_{sl} between the solid and a liquid based on a suitable model⁶.

An often applied model is the one of Owens, Wendt, Rabel and Kaelble (OWRK model)⁷ which considers the geometric mean of the dispersive and polar parts of the liquid's surface tension, γ_{lv} and of the solid's surface energy, γ_{sv} (Equation 3).

$$\gamma_{sl} = \gamma_{sv} + \gamma_{lv} - 2\sqrt{\gamma_{sv}^d \gamma_{lv}^d} - 2\sqrt{\gamma_{sv}^p \gamma_{lv}^p} \quad (3)$$

Substituting this expression in the Young's equation, the polar and the dispersive part of the **solid's surface free energy**, γ_{sv} can be determined from the regression line in a suitable plot as shown in Figure 4.

⁶ https://www.dataphysics-instruments.com/products/oca/?gclid=Cj0KCQjw-daUBhCIARIsALbkjSacqUsoQ6tnvS8x4jshTsVqZvgvVusRsFnFgCAVVpgkEFNCstzochcaAvQAEALw_wcB, consulted on 2022-05-31

⁷ ISO 19403-2:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 2: Determination of the surface free energy of solid surfaces by measuring the contact angle

Figure 4 – Regression line for determination of surface energy

The linear regression requires contact angle measurements with at least two different test liquids. However, as a regression line based on just two points contains no information on the accuracy of the result, therefore contact angle measurements with at least three test liquids are recommended for the determination of the surface energy of solids.

Measuring the surface energy of flat surfaces.

The relevant ISO standard here is ISO 19403-2:2017⁸. Despite its application is described for paints and varnished, it is also generally used to all types of solid surfaces and liquids. It describes the test method to measure the contact angle θ_c to determine the surface free energy s_s of solid surfaces. It suggests various test liquids with known surface tension values, but mostly water and di-iodomethane are used for such measurements. The test method consists of at least 3 drops from a micro syringe of at least 2 different liquids on a surface of a test specimen. Contact angles are measured, and the arithmetic mean value is further used, with a certain evaluation model, to calculate the surface free energy s_s . To measure the contact angle, an image of the droplet on the specimen is digitally captured from the side.

⁸ ISO 19403-2:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 2: Determination of the surface free energy of solid surfaces by measuring the contact angle

Recommended further reading

General reading

- Shivanjali Saxena and Rakesh Joshi, Microfluidic Devices: Applications and Role of Surface Wettability in Its Fabrication, 21st Century Surface Science - a Handbook.
- Joshi R, Chibber R. Development and interface characterization of unmatched glass-metal joint. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*. 2018; 31:787-800
- Joanny, J. F., & De Gennes, P. G. (1984). A model for contact angle hysteresis. *The journal of chemical physics*, 81(1), 552-562.
- Origins of Wetting by Charles W. Extrand:
<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/pdf/10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b01935>
- [<https://www.nanoscience.com/techniques/tensiometry/>]

Measurement of contact angle in circular channels

- Heshmati, M., & Piri, M. (2014). Experimental investigation of dynamic contact angle and capillary rise in tubes with circular and noncircular cross sections. *Langmuir*, 30(47), 14151-14162.
- Ehlers, S., Könemann, J., Ott, O., Wolf, H., Šetina, J., Furtado, A., & Sabuga, W. (2019). Selection and characterization of liquids for a low pressure interferometric liquid column manometer. *Measurement*, 132, 191-198.
- A. Olanrewaju, M. Beaugrand, M. Yafia and D. Juncker, *Lab Chip*, 2018, **18**, 2323 DOI: 10.1039/C8LC00458G. Capillary microfluidics in microchannels: from microfluidic networks to capillary circuits.
- Son S, Chen L, Kang Q, Derome D, Carmeliet J. Contact Angle Effects on Pore and Corner Arc Menisci in Polygonal Capillary Tubes Studied with the Pseudopotential Multiphase Lattice Boltzmann Model. *Computation*. 2016; 4(1):12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computation4010012>
- Valteri Heiskanen, Kalle Marjanen, Pasi Kallio, Machine Vision Based Measurement of Dynamic Contact Angles in Microchannel Flows, *Journal of Bionic Engineering*, Volume 5, Issue 4, 2008, Pages 282-290, ISSN 1672-6529, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1672-6529\(08\)60172-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1672-6529(08)60172-9)
- Jafari, Mohammad, and Jongwon Jung. 2017. "Direct Measurement of Static and Dynamic Contact Angles Using a Random Micromodel Considering Geological CO2 Sequestration" *Sustainability* 9, no. 12: 2352. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9122352>

Appendix: Alternative methods for measuring a contact angle⁹

- **Drop shape analysis:** The contact angle is measured using the image of a sessile drop at the points of intersection (three-phase contact points) between the drop contour and the projection of the surface (baseline).
- **Wilhelmy plate method:** The force acting in the tensile direction when moving a plate-shaped solid vertically in a liquid is measured. This force depends on the contact angle as well as on the surface tension and the wetted length. (According to ISO 304:1985¹⁰
- **Powder contact angle measurement using the Washburn method:** The increase in weight of an immersed powder-filled tube is measured with respect to time. The rate of rise of the liquid column depends, among other things, on the contact angle.
- **Top-view distance method:** The curvature of the drop surface associated with the contact angle is measured using the distance between light spots which are reflected on the top of a drop surface.
- **Dynamic Contact Angle:** Heshmati & Piri¹¹ focused their investigations on the direct measurement of dynamic contact angle and its variation with the velocity of the moving meniscus (or capillary number) in capillary rise experiments.
- **Image processing:** The drop is viewed in profile during the contact angle measurement. The image processing software recognises and records the drop contour, as well as the base line at the solid-liquid interface and fits a mathematical function to the drop shape.¹²
- **Plate method** to measure the contact angle is proposed by Ehlers *et al.*¹³ (Here the surface tension of the test liquid is determined via plate method.

In the static method, a thermally controlled fluid surface is brought into contact with a plate hanging on a precise balance. When touching the surface, the balance starts the measurement. With an assumed contact angle, θ_e of 0° of the platinum plate and its known geometry, the surface tension of the fluid is calculated. Repeating the experiment with the plate from the material under study and considering the measured tension, the solid-liquid-vapor contact angle is calculated using Equation 4, which corresponds to the ratio of the surface force F to the (wetted) length, L along which the force acts.

$$\gamma_{lv} = \frac{F}{L} \cos(\theta_e) \quad (4)$$

In the dynamic method, the plate already immersed into the liquid is moved up and down. The depth of the immersion and the movement speed are accurately measured, while the full cycle is repeated five times. By measuring the force when moving the plate up and down and taking into

⁹ <https://www.kruss-scientific.com/en/know-how/glossary/contact-angle>, consulted on 2022-05-31.

¹⁰ ISO 304:1985 (reviewed in 2019); Surface active agents – Determination of surface tension by drawing up liquid films and Technical Corrigendum (1998)

¹¹ Heshmati, M., & Piri, M. (2014). Experimental investigation of dynamic contact angle and capillary rise in tubes with circular and noncircular cross sections. *Langmuir*, 30(47), 14151-14162.

¹² https://www.dataphysics-instruments.com/products/oca/?gclid=Cj0KCQjw-daUBhCIARIsALbkjSacqUsOQ6tnvS8x4JshTsVqZvgvVusRsFnFgCAVVpgkEFNCstzochcaAvQAEALw_wcB, consulted on 2022-05-31

¹³ Ehlers, S., Könnemann, J., Ott, O., Wolf, H., Šetina, J., Furtado, A., & Sabuga, W. (2019). Selection and characterization of liquids for a low pressure interferometric liquid column manometer. *Measurement*, 132, 191-198.

account the buoyancy effect, the advancing and receding contact angles and, thus, the contact angle hysteresis is determined.

Figure 5: Platinum and PTFE Wilhelmy plates used with the Lauda TE3 tensiometer used by Ehlers *et al.*¹⁴

An overview of standards for tensiometers can be found at:

<https://www.bioline.com/attension/standards-for-tensiometers#force-tensiometers>

As mentioned previously, there are methods described in literature about the measurement of contact angles in microfluidic channels.

Dynamic Contact Angle: Heshmati & Piri¹⁵ focused their investigations on the direct measurement of dynamic contact angle and its variation with the velocity of the moving meniscus (or capillary number) in capillary rise experiments.

¹⁴ Ehlers, S., Könemann, J., Ott, O., Wolf, H., Šetina, J., Furtado, A., & Sabuga, W. (2019). Selection and characterization of liquids for a low pressure interferometric liquid column manometer. *Measurement*, 132, 191-198.

¹⁵ Heshmati, M., & Piri, M. (2014). Experimental investigation of dynamic contact angle and capillary rise in tubes with circular and noncircular cross sections. *Langmuir*, 30(47), 14151-14162.